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FOOD INTERACTIONS WITH LEVOTHYROXINE

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Levothyroxine, a synthetic thyroid hormone, was the most prescribed drug in the USA in the past three years. Levothyroxine is applied as substitution therapy in hypothyroidism (both primary and central) and also recommended after a thyroidectomy (without hypothyroidism) for the prevention of recurrences, for the inhibition of nodular goitre growth, after an operation of differentiated thyroid carcinoma, as well as after the neck radiation (in cancer prophylaxis). The main aim of this study was to determine the possible interactions of different food with levothyroxine by searching the Pubmed database.

The absorption of levothyroxine may be decreased by foods such as soy, walnuts, dietary fibres, cottonseed meal, calcium carbonate and iron supplements. Grapefruit juice delayed the absorption of levothyroxine, but did not affect its overall availability, according to a randomized cross-over study. Soy milk reduced the thyroxine plasma levels in two women with congenital hypothyroidism on levothyroxine substitution therapy. Both dietary fibres and calcium carbonate by nonspecific adsorption decreased the levothyroxine bioavailability. Concomitant ingestion of levothyroxine and iron supplements has resulted in the need to increase the levothyroxine dosage in pregnant women. The administration of levothyroxine swallowed with coffee/espresso lowered the peak values of thyroxine in the blood plasma, suggesting that the coffee interference with levothyroxine absorption.

Optimal levothyroxine absorption occurs when the stomach is empty; hence patients should take levothyroxine on an empty stomach 60 minutes before any food intake. The simplest regimen is for the patients to take the levothyroxine daily dosage immediately on waking in the morning with water and an hour before any food intake.

Keywords: levothyroxine, interactions, soy, grapefruit, coffee